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eimport numpy as np
import pandas as pd
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
from sklearn.preprocessing import StandardScaler
from sklearn.svm import SVC
from sklearn.linear_model import LogisticRegression
from sklearn.neighbors import KNeighborsClassifier
from sklearn.naive_bayes import GaussianNB
from sklearn.ensemble import RandomForestClassifier
from sklearn.metrics import (
    accuracy_score,
    precision_score,
    recall_score,
    f1_score,
    roc_auc_score,
    roc_curve,
    confusion_matrix,
)
import time
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import seaborn as sns

# Load your credit card fraud dataset (replace 'creditcard.csv' with your dataset file)
df = pd.read_csv('creditcard.csv')

# Split the dataset into features (X) and target (y)
X = df.drop('Class', axis=1)
y = df['Class']

# Split the data into a single train-test split
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X_train, X_test, y_train, y_test = train_test_split(X, y, test_size=0.2, random_state=42)

# Standardize features (important for some algorithms)
scaler = StandardScaler()
X_train = scaler.fit_transform(X_train)
X_test = scaler.transform(X_test)

# Initialize classifiers
classifiers = {
    'SVM': SVC(probability=True), # Note: Set probability=True for ROC AUC calculation
    'Logistic Regression': LogisticRegression(),
    'K-Nearest Neighbors': KNeighborsClassifier(),
    'Gaussian Naive Bayes': GaussianNB(),
    'Random Forest': RandomForestClassifier(n_estimators=100, random_state=42)
}

# Initialize an empty list to store the dictionaries of metrics for each classifier
metrics_list = []

# Evaluate each classifier on the single train-test split
for name, clf in classifiers.items():
    print(f"Classifier: {name}")

    # Record start time for evaluation
    start_time = time.time()

    try:
        clf.fit(X_train, y_train)
    except Exception as e:
        print(f"Error occurred while fitting {name}: {str(e)}")
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    continue

# Predict on the test set
y_pred = clf.predict(X_test)

# Calculate evaluation metrics
accuracy = accuracy_score(y_test, y_pred)
precision = precision_score(y_test, y_pred)
recall = recall_score(y_test, y_pred)
f1 = f1_score(y_test, y_pred)

# Predict probabilities for positive class (fraud)
y_prob = clf.predict_proba(X_test)[:, 1]

# Calculate ROC AUC
roc_auc = roc_auc_score(y_test, y_prob)

# Record end time for evaluation
end_time = time.time()

# Calculate execution time
execution_time = end_time - start_time

# Append metrics to the list
metrics_list.append({
    'Classifier': name,
    'Accuracy': accuracy,
    'Precision': precision,
    'Recall': recall,
    'F1 Score': f1,
```

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    'ROC AUC': roc_auc
})

# Print metrics for each classifier
print(f"Execution Time: {execution_time:.2f} seconds")
print(f"Accuracy: {accuracy}")
print(f"Precision: {precision}")
print(f"Recall: {recall}")
print(f"F1 Score: {f1}")
print(f"ROC AUC: {roc_auc}")
print("=" * 50)

# Plot the confusion matrix
plt.figure(figsize=(8, 6))
cm = confusion_matrix(y_test, y_pred)
sns.heatmap(cm, annot=True, fmt='d', cmap='Blues', cbar=False)
plt.title(f'Confusion Matrix for {name}')
plt.xlabel('Predicted')
plt.ylabel('Actual')
plt.show()

# Plot ROC AUC curve
fpr, tpr, _ = roc_curve(y_test, y_prob)
plt.figure(figsize=(8, 6))
plt.plot(fpr, tpr, label=f'{name} (AUC = {roc_auc:.2f})')
plt.plot([0, 1], [0, 1], linestyle='--', color='gray')
plt.xlabel('False Positive Rate')
plt.ylabel('True Positive Rate')
plt.title(f'ROC Curve for {name}')
plt.legend(loc='lower right')

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plt.show()

# Create a DataFrame from the list of metrics
metrics_df = pd.DataFrame(metrics_list)

# Print the metrics DataFrame
print("\nPerformance Metrics for Classifiers:")
print(metrics_df)
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```
Classifier: SVM
Execution Time: 1688.90 seconds
Accuracy: 0.9993153330290369
Precision: 0.9682539682539683
Recall: 0.6224489795918368
F1 Score: 0.7577639751552796
ROC AUC: 0.9618443360743284
=====
Classifier: Logistic Regression
Execution Time: 2.06 seconds
Accuracy: 0.9991222218320986
Precision: 0.8636363636363636
Recall: 0.5816326530612245
F1 Score: 0.6951219512195121
ROC AUC: 0.9747392274298577
=====
Classifier: K-Nearest Neighbors
Execution Time: 67.25 seconds
Accuracy: 0.9995259997893332
Precision: 0.9382716049382716
Recall: 0.7755102040816326
F1 Score: 0.8491620111731844
ROC AUC: 0.9335599690776705
=====
Classifier: Gaussian Naive Bayes
Execution Time: 0.27 seconds
Accuracy: 0.9778273234788104
Precision: 0.06037735849056604
Recall: 0.8163265306122449
F1 Score: 0.11243851018973998
ROC AUC: 0.9671064437311221
=====
Classifier: Random Forest
Execution Time: 291.67 seconds
Accuracy: 0.9995611109160493
Precision: 0.974025974025974
Recall: 0.7653061224489796
F1 Score: 0.8571428571428571
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ROC AUC: 0.9476120252546714

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classifier: SVM

Execution Time: 1759.07 seconds

Accuracy: 0.9993153330290369

Precision: 0.9682539682539683

Recall: 0.6224489795918368

F1 Score: 0.7577639751552796

ROC AUC: 0.9618443360743284

Confusion Matrix for SVM

Classifier: Logistic Regression
 Execution Time: 1.84 seconds
 Accuracy: 0.9991222218320986
 Precision: 0.8636363636363636
 Recall: 0.5816326530612245
 F1 Score: 0.6951219512195121
 ROC AUC: 0.9747392274298577

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Confusion Matrix for Logistic Regression

Classifier: K-Nearest Neighbors
Execution Time: 71.15 seconds
Accuracy: 0.9995259997893332
Precision: 0.9382716049382716
Recall: 0.7755102040816326
F1 Score: 0.8491620111731844
ROC AUC: 0.9335599690776705

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Confusion Matrix for K-Nearest Neighbors

Classifier: Gaussian Naive Bayes
Execution Time: 0.24 seconds
Accuracy: 0.9778273234788104
Precision: 0.06037735849056604
Recall: 0.8163265306122449
F1 Score: 0.11243851018973998
ROC AUC: 0.9671064437311221

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Confusion Matrix for Gaussian Naive Bayes

Classifier: Random Forest
 Execution Time: 337.84 seconds
 Accuracy: 0.9995611109160493
 Precision: 0.974025974025974
 Recall: 0.7653061224489796
 F1 Score: 0.8571428571428571
 ROC AUC: 0.9476120252546714

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Confusion Matrix for Random Forest

ROC Curve for Random Forest

